

Anigraphical Etude 9

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The Anigraphical Etude #9 is an interactive music manuscript in “1st person shooter” video game format for live concert performance for flute. The game play is based upon Robert Frost’s *The Death of the Hired Man*. The performer navigates a 3D performance space as the character Silas before a concert audience. This performance features flutist Elizabeth Stern, a student of Carnegie Mellon School of Music faculty members Jeanne Baxtresser and Alberto Almarza.